

Hello ,

We are approaching the halfway mark for HumanTech! It is the perfect time to share the highlights of our latest developments and our next steps to continue building a safer, greener and more efficient European construction industry.

After celebrating [#1YearofHumanTech](#), we had the opportunity to reconnect in person at our last General Assembly Meeting in Oslo (Norway). Colleagues from our 21 partner organisations took the opportunity to share their achievements and challenges since we began working together and to align future plans. We could also witness how our technologies were starting to take shape and discuss how to contribute to the training resources we will develop to upskill and re-skill construction professionals.

Since then, we have continued to share the benefits of our technologies and our human-centred approach to developing them, strengthen collaboration in our Tech4EUConstruction cluster or share the stories of our colleagues dedicated to research.

We are now moving forward and are prepared for HumanTech's next phase. Will you join us?

[Check our latest progress and next steps](#)

[Learn more about HumanTech](#) | Watch the interview we did in Oslo with our project coordinator, Jason Rambach, to better understand our objectives and innovative solutions to address construction workers' safety and well-being as well as environmental sustainability and efficiency in the building sector. [Also, check Part 2](#) to learn how we address the main challenges facing the EU construction sector!

What is HumanTech?

Jason Rambach

HumanTech Project Coordinator

Funded by
the European Union

humantech

Now, let's dive into our updates, insightful stories, opportunities, resources and inspiration on construction innovation. Enjoy!

HumanTech Stories

[User-centred development: Evaluating HumanTech technologies for a safer, greener construction](#)

Through our work in **human factors, usability training and evaluation**, we are creating and delivering educational resources to improve the health, safety and green skills in construction. Discover how we assess workers' technology acceptance and the results of the user evaluation focus groups we have organised so far in Spain and Ireland.

[Implenia at KOMMUNALE Congress 2023: Showcasing innovations in construction](#)

Our Implenia partners took part in the latest KOMMUNALE Congress in Nürnberg, Germany, where they presented their research work at HumanTech and showcased some of their technological solutions for the construction sector.

Next HumanTech events

We will participate in more events during the next months:

- **20 November 2023: [SBS Construction Forum 2023](#)**. Our partners at the European Builders Confederation (EBC) are co-organising this event dedicated to the Construction Products Regulation.
- **January 4-8, 2024: [Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision \(WACV\)](#)**, where we will present our semantic segmentation work on panoramic images with depth information.
- **March 13-15, 2024: [European Robotics Forum \(ERF\) 2024](#)**, where we will hold a workshop on "AI and Robotics in Construction" with our sister projects for the second year in

a row.

[Tech4EUConstruction cluster launches #WordsOfInnovation campaign](#)

Through this social media campaign, experts from HumanTech and the other founding projects of our Tech4Construction cluster, BEEYONDERS and RoBétArmé, are exploring and clarifying the meaning of essential keywords to understand today's construction sector. Check it out on [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#).

[We celebrate our General Assembly Meeting in Oslo](#)

Our team met from 23 to 25 August 2023 for our yearly General Assembly Meeting. We discussed human-robot collaboration, wearable technology, and construction workers' perception of health and safety innovation, shared our milestones and agreed on our next steps.

Meet the #HumanTechTeam

Unlocking the
future of research

"HumanTech has played a pivotal role in my thesis research, enabling me to understand the rationale behind XR utilisation, the strategies employed to incorporate AR into the project and the potential advantages of its adoption."

HARSH MANOJ SHAH

Master's student at the Technical University of Munich

Get inspired by the latest stories from our "Unlocking the Future of Research" editorial series. Meet our colleagues pursuing a research career — from PhDs to junior researchers — and learn how working in HumanTech can influence their careers.

- [Irati Rasines](#), PhD student at the University of the Basque Country and Tecnalía: "The focus of my study is to enable robots to learn from human operators based on a few demonstrations performed via teleoperation."
- [Harsh Manoj Shah](#), master's student at the Technical University of Munich and working student at Holo-Light GmbH: "My thesis is centred around Extended Reality (XR) adoption within industrial firms and its profound impact on value creation and customer experience."

- [Mahdi Chamseddine](#), PhD student at RTPU Kaiserslautern working in the Augmented Vision department of DFKI: "My research focuses on deep learning for sensor data processing and scene understanding, specifically using radar and lidar sensors."

Stay tuned for more captivating stories from our exceptional researchers!

Tech4EUconstruction

#Tech4EUconstruction

Together with our sister projects, we are on a journey to address key challenges of the European construction sector.

[Learn more about our cluster](#)

BEEYONDERS · [Building more, building greener. How robots can help the construction sector grow bigger and more sustainable](#) | Going digital can be crucial for global construction, but SMEs struggle to keep pace. Hence, the robot challenge in the AI era: filling the gap with the big industry and letting the whole sector grow bigger and greener.

[RoBétArmé's newsletter #3](#) | Discover the RoBétARmé Project's latest updates and developments.

Beyond HumanTech

Opportunities to take action and inspiration from our sector.

- [Interested in learning about drones for construction?](#) This course from our partner, the Technological University of the Shannon (TUS), provides learners with the relevant

knowledge and skills in the operations of on-site procedures in this sector, and aircraft technical and maintenance specifications. Learners will build their knowledge of flight limitations and emergency procedures and develop skills to ensure safe and efficient use of Drone captured data with training in drone flight operations.

- Are you an ICT standardisation expert? [Apply to StandICT.eu's open call up until 9 January 2024](#), which will provide € 2,925,000 of funding to support the participation of European standardisation specialists in key international and global SDOs. *They are looking for experts with a special focus on 6G, citiverse and digital product passport.
- Check out the EU-funded REINCARNATE latest scientific publication on "[Data-driven of Alkali-activated concrete using Sequential Learning \(SL\)](#)" in the Journal of Cleaner Production. It presents a novel approach for developing sustainable building materials through ecologically informed SL, proving that by adopting a data-driven approach, sustainable building materials can be developed much quicker than commonly anticipated.

To finish, one last recommendation

[The World's Best Construction Podcast, by the B1M](#)

☐It is for you if you are interested in the largest and most mind-blowing construction projects going on around the world.

Thanks for reading,
The HumanTech Team

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